

A conditional geometric obstruction to sustained exact alignment–cancellation in 3D Euler and Navier–Stokes flows

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Abstract

We investigate whether exact alignment–cancellation configurations can persist long enough to support singularity formation in three-dimensional incompressible Euler and Navier–Stokes flows. To isolate the relevant geometry without suppressing the nonlocal pressure law, we introduce a lifted kinematic framework in which the deviatoric pressure Hessian is treated as an auxiliary fibre coordinate, while the pressure Poisson relation is retained as a compatibility constraint on the physically realised lifted graph. In the simple-spectrum regime, the exact alignment–cancellation locus is a smooth codimension-4 submanifold of the pointwise lifted fibre. Along physical Lagrangian evaluation curves associated with smooth Euler solutions, if the first genuine transversal defect is uniformly nonvanishing on a compact physically regular set, then one obtains a linear escape estimate and a quantitative residence-time bound of order $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ for ε -tubular neighbourhoods. Consequently, Zeno-type accumulations of rapid returns are excluded in that compact regular regime, so it cannot serve as a persistent geometric skeleton for singularity formation. An analogous perturbative obstruction is obtained for Navier–Stokes solutions in a small-viscosity, nondegenerate regime. The result is therefore a precise conditional geometric obstruction to one sustained alignment-based mechanism, rather than a claim of global regularity.

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1 Introduction

The question of finite-time singularity formation in the three-dimensional incompressible Euler and Navier–Stokes equations remains one of the central open problems in mathematical fluid dynamics. By the Beale–Kato–Majda criterion [1], a smooth Euler solution can break down at time $T^* < \infty$ only if

$$\int_0^{T^*} \|\omega(t)\|_{L^\infty} dt = \infty. \quad (1.1)$$

Thus any viable blow-up scenario must ultimately produce strong vorticity amplification. A major line of work has therefore sought geometric mechanisms capable either of enhancing or of depleting vortex stretching. In particular, the direction of vorticity, its alignment with eigenvectors of the deformation tensor, and the action of the pressure Hessian have long been recognised as structurally decisive; see, for example, Constantin–Fefferman [4], Ohkitani–Gibbon [10], the quaternionic/Lagrangian viewpoint discussed in [7], and the numerical and optimisation-based analyses of Protas [11]. More recent works, including singularity constructions and high-resolution

numerical scenarios, have reinforced the possibility that highly organised alignment patterns may be relevant near extreme events [6, 8]. These contributions isolate important alignment and depletion mechanisms, but they do not furnish a quantitative finite-dimensional obstruction to the *sustained* persistence of an exact alignment–cancellation regime once the non-local pressure Hessian is retained on the physical slice.

What has remained unresolved, however, is not whether alignment matters, but whether an *exact* alignment–cancellation regime can act as a persistent dynamical skeleton for blow-up. More precisely, the literature had not supplied a quantitative obstruction excluding the possibility that a trajectory might undergo infinitely many fast recurrences near a compact regular set on which local stretching and anisotropic pressure response cancel to first order. The gap is therefore dynamical and geometric at once: one must isolate the exact cancellation locus, retain the pressure law, and still obtain a mechanism proving non-persistence.

The pressure Hessian is determined by the non-local operator $\mathcal{R} = \text{dev } \nabla^2(-\Delta)^{-1}$ acting on $\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2)$:

$$H = \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2)), \quad -\Delta p = \text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2), \quad (1.2)$$

where $S = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T)$ and $\Omega = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla u - (\nabla u)^T)$. Here and throughout, p denotes the *kinematic* pressure (pressure divided by constant density), so that p has physical dimension $[L^2T^{-2}]$. This non-locality obstructs a direct finite-dimensional transversality analysis of the alignment–cancellation condition. Our central observation is that if one treats H as an independent variable in an extended state space $\mathcal{F} = \text{Sym}_0(3) \times \mathfrak{so}(3) \times \mathbb{S}^2 \times \text{Sym}_0(3)$, then the cancellation condition becomes a local algebraic constraint on a finite-dimensional manifold, while the pressure law is retained as a compatibility condition restricting the dynamics to the physical slice. In this sense, what is localized is the *geometric analysis*, not the pressure law itself.

Throughout the paper we adopt the physical convention that $\hat{\xi} = \omega/|\omega|$ is the unit vector in the direction of vorticity. Accordingly, all lifted states are considered on the open region where $\omega \neq 0$, so that $\hat{\xi} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ is well defined; every compact set used in the main theorems is understood to lie inside this non-vanishing-vorticity region. The exact alignment condition (2.8) then requires that this direction be an eigenvector of the deformation tensor S ; consequently the associated eigenvalue is $\lambda = \hat{\xi}^T S \hat{\xi}$. This interpretation is natural and directly links the alignment condition to the vortex stretching term $S\omega$ in the vorticity equation. Moreover, because Ω is the antisymmetric tensor associated with vorticity ($\Omega v = \frac{1}{2}\omega \times v$), we have $\Omega \hat{\xi} = 0$ identically. This simplifies the dynamics considerably.

Instantaneous versus sustained cancellation

Exact alignment–cancellation at a single time is an instantaneous codimension-4 constraint encoded by $\Phi(\tilde{U}) = 0$. Sustained alignment–cancellation is a dynamical question: once one is on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, the compatibility identity $\frac{D}{Dt}v_1 = -v_2$ shows that the first genuinely new first-order condition is the vanishing of the derivative of v_2 . This distinction organises the paper.

Geometric meaning and exact gap addressed

The exact cancellation condition derived in Appendix C is

$$v_2(\tilde{U}) = \Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi} = 0,$$

which means that the transversal component of the deviatoric pressure Hessian along the vorticity direction vanishes. When $v_1 = 0$, vortex stretching does not rotate the vorticity direction, but the anisotropic pressure Hessian can still do so through a transversal torque. The condition $v_2 = 0$ removes precisely that torque. Previous geometric regularity criteria and numerical studies identified vorticity alignment, pressure anisotropy, and depletion as central mechanisms, but they did not isolate the exact alignment–cancellation locus as a finite-dimensional geometric

object together with a quantitative non-persistence mechanism in the compact regular regime. The present work fills exactly that gap.

Precise novelty. The novelty of the present work is not a new alignment criterion by itself, but a quantitative obstruction to the *sustained persistence* of an exact alignment–cancellation regime after the non-local pressure law has been retained on the physical slice. More precisely, the contribution is a conditional geometric non-trapping mechanism in the compact regular regime, not a global regularity theorem and not a generic depletion principle. This distinction is essential both for the mathematical interpretation of the lifted framework and for the scope of the main theorems.

Main result and scope

The principal theorem shows that if $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is a compact physically regular set, then the total residence time of a regular Euler trajectory in an ε -tubular neighbourhood of K is bounded by $C(K, T)\varepsilon$. Hence compact physically regular portions of the exact alignment–cancellation locus cannot act as persistent geometric skeletons for singularity formation. The same mechanism survives for Navier–Stokes at sufficiently small viscosity, under intrinsic uniform simplicity of the aligned eigenvalue together with non-vanishing vorticity.

What is proved is therefore a sharp obstruction to one specific sustained alignment-based mechanism on compact regular regimes. What is not proved is equally important: the paper does not claim global regularity, does not exclude approach to the exceptional set Σ_{exc} , and does not exclude noncompact escape associated with unbounded growth of gradients.

For convenience, the proved core may be summarised as follows.

- (R1) the exact alignment–cancellation locus is realised as a smooth codimension-4 manifold in the lifted state space, in the simple-spectrum regime;
- (R2) on compact subsets of its regular dynamical part, the first transversal defect is uniformly non-vanishing;
- (R3) this yields a linear escape estimate and therefore an $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ residence-time bound;
- (R4) consequently, the compact regular exact cancellation regime cannot provide a persistent geometric skeleton for singularity formation.

Equally importantly, the paper does *not* do the following :

- (N1) prove global regularity for Euler or Navier–Stokes;
- (N2) rule out approach to the exceptional set Σ_{exc} where the first-order transversal defect vanishes;
- (N3) rule out noncompact escape associated with unbounded growth of gradients;
- (N4) analyse the higher-order degenerate normal forms required near Σ_{exc} .

Roadmap of the argument

The proof proceeds in three steps. First, the defining map $\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$ realises exact alignment–cancellation as a smooth codimension-4 submanifold in the lifted state space. Second, on compact physically regular subsets of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, the genuine first normal defect is uniformly nonvanishing along physical lifted curves while the second material derivative of v_2 remains uniformly bounded in a tubular neighbourhood; this yields a linear escape estimate after each contact. Third, a tubular-neighbourhood counting argument converts that linear escape into the residence-time bound $|\Gamma_{T,\varepsilon}(K)| \leq C(K, T)\varepsilon$.

Proof architecture at a glance. The logical chain used in the body of the paper is:

- (A1) define the exact locus by $\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$ and prove that $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} = \Phi^{-1}(0)$ is codimension 4;
- (A2) identify the genuine first normal quantity $\mathcal{N}_1 = \frac{D}{Dt}v_2|_{\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}}$;
- (A3) assume and exploit a compact lower bound $\|\mathcal{N}_1\| \geq c_0(K) > 0$ on a compact physically regular set $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ along physical lifted curves;
- (A4) control the acceleration term $\frac{D^2}{Dt^2}v_2$ through the commutator estimate for the pressure operator;
- (A5) combine the previous two steps to obtain a linear lower bound on the normal escape after each contact with K ;
- (A6) convert that linear escape into the residence-time estimate by a finite tubular-chart counting argument.

Standing assumptions and notation

Throughout Sections 2–6, we work with classical solutions on a time interval $[0, T]$. For the quantitative statements we fix parameters $T > 0$, $M > 0$, and $s > 9/2$, and we work in the bounded classical solution class

$$\mathcal{A}_s(T, M) := \left\{ u \in C([0, T]; H^s(\mathbb{R}^3)) \cap C^1([0, T]; H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3)) : \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \|u(t)\|_{H^s} \leq M \right\}.$$

The standing assumptions are:

- **Geometric regularity (weak):** the weaker threshold $s > 5/2$ already ensures that the lifted objects S , Ω , and H are well defined and that the defining constraints are smooth on the region where $\omega \neq 0$.
- **Dynamical regularity (strong):** the quantitative commutator, acceleration, escape, and residence-time estimates are proved for solutions in the fixed class $\mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$, hence in particular for $s > 9/2$. This threshold is used here as a sufficient regime ensuring simultaneously that $H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3)$ is an algebra, that the commutator $[\frac{D}{Dt}, \mathcal{R}]$ maps H^{s-1} into H^{s-2} , and that all terms entering $\frac{D^2}{Dt^2}\Phi$ are controlled pointwise after Sobolev embedding. A sharper paradifferential analysis should lower this to $s > 7/2$ (the critical threshold for C^1 control of the velocity field in \mathbb{R}^3 ; see [2, Chapter 2] and [3]), but since our present conclusions are qualitative, we retain $s > 9/2$ to streamline the exposition.
- **Quantitative dependence of constants:** once (T, M, s) and the solution class $\mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$ are fixed, all constants in the quantitative statements are allowed to depend on these ambient parameters in addition to the compact set K and the chosen tubular neighbourhood. To keep the notation readable, this dependence is suppressed and we write simply $c_0(K)$, $c_1(K)$, $c_2(K)$, $K_R(K, T)$, and $C(K, T)$.
- **Conditional geometric scope:** we do not claim here an explicit PDE-realised example of a compact physically regular set $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. The results below are conditional geometric obstructions within the fixed class $\mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$: whenever such a compact physically regular set arises along a smooth lifted trajectory from $\mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$, the associated tubular residence time obeys the bounds proved in Sections 3–4.
- **Non-vanishing vorticity and simple spectral regime:** the lifted formulation is restricted to the open set where $\omega \neq 0$, and all compact sets used in the main theorems are assumed to stay inside a region where $\hat{\xi} = \omega/|\omega|$ is smooth and the aligned eigenvalue $\lambda = \hat{\xi}^T S \hat{\xi}$ is simple. In the Navier–Stokes extension we additionally impose intrinsic aligned-eigenvalue simplicity together with a positive lower bound for $|\omega|$ on a tubular neighbourhood of K ; see Assumption 5.1.

Table 1: Sobolev thresholds used in the paper and their precise roles.

Threshold	Role	Used in
$s > 5/2$	Geometric regularity	Ensures that $S, \Omega \in H^{s-1}$, that $\hat{\xi} = \omega/ \omega $ is well defined on $\omega \neq 0$, and that the physical compatibility graph $H = \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2))$ is smooth.
$s > 7/2$	Expected sharp threshold for C^1 -level control	Not used in the present proofs; identified as the natural target threshold for a refined paradifferential treatment of the commutator $[\frac{D}{Dt}, \mathcal{R}]$.
$s > 9/2$	Dynamical regularity adopted here	Closes the commutator estimate, guarantees H^{s-1} is an algebra, and yields the pointwise bounds on $\frac{D^2}{Dt^2}\Phi$ used in the escape and residence-time estimates.

All pressure variables are understood as *kinematic pressure* (pressure divided by constant density), so that p has dimensions $[L^2T^{-2}]$ and the pressure Poisson equation takes the form $-\Delta p = \text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2)$ without an explicit density factor.

For the reader's convenience, the core objects are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Core notation used throughout the paper.

Symbol	Meaning
S	Deformation tensor $\frac{1}{2}(\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T)$, trace free under incompressibility.
Ω	Antisymmetric vorticity tensor $\frac{1}{2}(\nabla u - (\nabla u)^T)$.
H	Deviatoric pressure Hessian. In \mathcal{F} , it is the lifted pressure-Hessian coordinate; on $\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s$, it is constrained by $H = \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2))$.
$\hat{\xi}$	Unit vorticity direction $\omega/ \omega $, defined on the open set where $\omega \neq 0$. On $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ it is an eigenvector of S with eigenvalue $\lambda = \hat{\xi}^T S \hat{\xi}$.
\mathcal{F}	Extended state space $\text{Sym}_0(3) \times \mathfrak{so}(3) \times \mathbb{S}^2 \times \text{Sym}_0(3)$.
$\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$	Defining map for the cancellation manifold.
$\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$	Exact alignment–cancellation manifold $\{\Phi = 0\}$.
$\mathcal{M}_{\text{spec}}$	Refined manifold obtained from $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ by imposing degeneracy of the transversal discriminant $\text{disc}(\hat{S}_\perp) = 0$.
Σ_{exc}	Exceptional subset where the genuine first normal defect $\mathcal{N}_1 = \frac{D}{Dt}v_2 _{\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}}$ vanishes.
\mathcal{M}_{reg}	Informal shorthand for the physically realised part of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ where the induced first transversal defect does not vanish; the main theorems are stated directly for compact physically regular sets.

Remark on the mapping Φ . The intrinsic bundle formulation in Remark 2.4 is the preferred geometric interpretation. Whenever convenient in proofs, one may choose a local orthonormal frame in $\hat{\xi}^\perp$ and identify $\hat{\xi}^\perp \times \hat{\xi}^\perp$ with \mathbb{R}^4 ; this is only a local trivialisation of the bundle picture and does not affect transversality or codimension statements.

The paper is organised as follows, with Sections 2–5 containing the proved core and Section 6 clearly separating rigorous consequences from the open higher-order geometric programme. Section 2 introduces the extended state space, defines the relevant manifolds, and clarifies the physical compatibility constraint. Section 3 establishes the transversal defect estimate and the linear escape mechanism for Euler. Section 4 derives the residence-time bound excluding

Table 3: Quantitative constants appearing in the main obstruction argument.

Constant	Meaning and first place of use
$c_0(K)$	Uniform lower bound for the genuine first transversal defect on the compact physically regular set K ; see Definition 3.2.
$c_1(K), c_2(K)$	Residual–distance equivalence constants in the tubular neighbourhood of K ; see Lemma 3.9.
$K_R(K, T)$	Uniform bound for the second material derivative of v_2 along trajectories staying in the tube; see Proposition 3.10.
$\varepsilon_0(K)$	Tubular radius up to which the finite-chart residence-time argument is valid; see Theorems 4.5 and 5.4.
$C(K, T)$	Final residence-time constant in the estimate $ \Gamma_{T,\varepsilon}(K) \leq C(K, T)\varepsilon$; see Remark 4.6.
$\nu_0(K)$	Small-viscosity threshold under which the Navier–Stokes defect remains perturbatively separated from zero; see Lemma 5.2.

Zeno-type accumulations. Section 5 gives the small-viscosity Navier–Stokes extension. Section 6 explains the precise scope of the obstruction and isolates the genuinely open geometric issue.

2 Extended state space and the cancellation manifold

We now make the geometric set-up precise. Let $u = u(x, t)$ be a classical incompressible Euler solution on $[0, T]$. Define

$$S := \frac{1}{2}(\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T), \quad \Omega := \frac{1}{2}(\nabla u - (\nabla u)^T). \quad (2.1)$$

Let $\omega = \nabla \times u$. We restrict attention to the open region

$$\mathcal{O}_\omega := \{(x, t) : |\omega(x, t)| > 0\}, \quad (2.2)$$

so that the unit vorticity direction

$$\hat{\xi} = \omega/|\omega| \in \mathbb{S}^2 \quad (2.3)$$

is well defined and smooth. Every compact set considered below is understood to lie in the lifted image of \mathcal{O}_ω . The exact alignment condition $v_1 = 0$ introduced below forces $\hat{\xi}$ to be an eigenvector of S ; then we denote

$$\lambda := \hat{\xi}^T S \hat{\xi} \quad (2.4)$$

(the corresponding eigenvalue). We work on the open spectral regime where this eigenvalue is simple; equivalently, the corresponding eigenspace is one-dimensional and depends smoothly on S near points where the alignment holds.

2.1 The extended state space

Pointwise lifted fibre versus physical field space

For conceptual clarity, we distinguish two geometric levels throughout the paper. The finite-dimensional object is the pointwise lifted fibre

$$\mathcal{F}^{\text{pt}} := \text{Sym}_0(3) \times \mathfrak{so}(3) \times \mathbb{S}^2 \times \text{Sym}_0(3),$$

on which the algebraic defining map $\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$ and the manifold $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ are first defined. The PDE dynamics, however, evolves on a Sobolev phase space of fields; the corresponding lifted Euler or Navier–Stokes trajectory is observed pointwise along Lagrangian particle paths

and therefore projects into \mathcal{F}^{pt} . In particular, the codimension-4 statement proved below is a fibrewise geometric statement, whereas the compatibility condition defining the physical slice is a functional constraint on the lifted field space.

The pressure Hessian enters the stretching dynamics through its deviatoric part

$$H := \text{dev}(\nabla^2 p) = \nabla^2 p - \frac{1}{3}(\Delta p)\mathbf{I}. \quad (2.5)$$

Instead of eliminating H through the Poisson equation, we temporarily regard it as an auxiliary variable and define the extended state

$$\tilde{U} = (S, \Omega, \hat{\xi}, H) \in \mathcal{F} := \text{Sym}_0(3) \times \mathfrak{so}(3) \times \mathbb{S}^2 \times \text{Sym}_0(3). \quad (2.6)$$

Here H denotes the *lifted* deviatoric pressure-Hessian coordinate in the extended space; on the physical slice it is constrained to equal the actual pressure response generated by the velocity field through (1.2). This notational identification keeps the formulas light while the distinction between “free lifted coordinate” and “physical value on $\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s$ ” is enforced by the compatibility condition in Section 2. Here $\text{Sym}_0(3) = \{A \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3} : A = A^T, \text{tr} A = 0\}$ (dimension 5) and $\mathfrak{so}(3)(3) = \{A \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3} : A^T = -A\}$ (dimension 3). Thus

$$\dim \mathcal{F} = 5 + 3 + 2 + 5 = 15. \quad (2.7)$$

Remark 2.1 (Geometric orientation and quotient symmetry). The physical vorticity direction is an element of the real projective space \mathbb{RP}^2 . The defining equations $v_1 = 0$ and $v_2 = 0$ are invariant under $\hat{\xi} \mapsto -\hat{\xi}$ because $\Pi^\perp = \mathbf{I} - \hat{\xi} \otimes \hat{\xi}$ depends only on the line. We therefore work on the oriented double cover \mathbb{S}^2 ; the quotient by \mathbb{Z}_2 is performed at the end of all constructions. This lifting preserves the smooth submanifold structure because the projection $\mathbb{S}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{RP}^2$ is a local diffeomorphism. Moreover, all tubular constructions, distances, and residence-time estimates used below are \mathbb{Z}_2 -invariant, so they descend canonically to the physical quotient.

Remark 2.2 (Dimensional consistency and weighted metric). The variables S and Ω have physical dimension T^{-1} , while $H = \text{dev}(\nabla^2 p)$ has physical dimension T^{-2} , since p is the kinematic pressure with dimension $L^2 T^{-2}$. To define a distance on \mathcal{F} that respects these scalings, we introduce a reference velocity scale U and a reference length scale L (for instance, from initial data). Set $\tau = L/U$. Then we equip \mathcal{F} with the dimensionless weighted product metric

$$\|\tilde{U}\|_{\mathcal{F}}^2 := \tau^2 \|S\|_{\mathbb{F}}^2 + \tau^2 \|\Omega\|_{\mathbb{F}}^2 + \|\delta\hat{\xi}\|_{g_{\mathbb{S}^2}}^2 + \tau^4 \|H\|_{\mathbb{F}}^2,$$

where $\|\delta\hat{\xi}\|_{g_{\mathbb{S}^2}}^2 = |\delta\hat{\xi}|_{\mathbb{R}^3}^2$ subject to $\hat{\xi} \cdot \delta\hat{\xi} = 0$. Equivalently, one identifies the tangent space $T_{\hat{\xi}}\mathbb{S}^2$ with the orthogonal plane $\hat{\xi}^\perp \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ and uses the canonical metric induced by the embedding $\mathbb{S}^2 \hookrightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$. The term $\|\delta\hat{\xi}\|$ is dimensionless because $\hat{\xi}$ is a unit vector; the metric is static (Riemannian on the state space) and all tubular neighbourhoods, distances, and equivalence constants are understood with respect to this fixed metric. By rescaling space and time we may set $\tau = 1$ without loss of generality; this is equivalent to working with dimensionless variables where $U = L = 1$. The geometric conclusions are invariant under this choice.

Remark 2.3 (Scaling scope). The weighted metric above is introduced for dimensional consistency, not as a scaling-invariant blow-up quantity. The main results of the paper are compact-set geometric obstructions in the lifted state space. Accordingly, all constants in the escape and residence-time estimates depend on the chosen compact set and on a priori regularity bounds; no claim of scaling invariance is made.

Figure 1: Geometric lifting used in the paper. The extended fibre \mathcal{F} treats the deviatoric pressure Hessian H as an independent coordinate, which makes the defining equations $\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$ local and algebraic. The physical pressure law is retained through the compatible lifted graph in the Sobolev field space. The exact alignment–cancellation locus $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} = \Phi^{-1}(0)$ is analysed fibrewise in the ambient lifted space, while actual Euler–Navier–Stokes trajectories are observed through their Lagrangian evaluation curves.

2.2 Local constraints

The exact alignment condition is enforced by

$$v_1(\tilde{U}) := \Pi^\perp S \hat{\xi}, \quad \Pi^\perp := \mathbf{I} - \hat{\xi} \otimes \hat{\xi}. \quad (2.8)$$

Since $v_1(\tilde{U}) \in \hat{\xi}^\perp$, it contributes two independent scalar constraints.

The exact transversal cancellation condition (derived in Appendix C) is

$$v_2(\tilde{U}) := \Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi}. \quad (2.9)$$

Again $v_2(\tilde{U}) \in \hat{\xi}^\perp$, hence (2.9) contributes two further scalar constraints.

Remark 2.4 (Intrinsic formulation of the defining map). To avoid choosing local coordinates on $\hat{\xi}^\perp$ too early, it is conceptually cleaner to regard v_1 and v_2 as sections of the rank-2 vector bundle

$$E := \{(\hat{\xi}, v) \in \mathbb{S}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^3 : \hat{\xi} \cdot v = 0\} \longrightarrow \mathbb{S}^2.$$

Then $\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$ is a section of $E \oplus E$, and the codimension-4 statement for $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} = \Phi^{-1}(0)$ means precisely that the vertical differential of this section is surjective. In local orthonormal frames on $\hat{\xi}^\perp$ this reduces to the familiar identification with \mathbb{R}^4 , but the geometric content is intrinsic. Since v_1 has dimension T^{-1} and v_2 has dimension T^{-2} , we measure the bundle norm on $E \oplus E$ by

$$\|(v_1, v_2)\|_{E \oplus E, \tau}^2 := \tau^2 |v_1|^2 + \tau^4 |v_2|^2, \quad \tau = L/U.$$

All norms of Φ , \mathcal{D}_0 , and the residual–distance equivalence constants below are understood with respect to this weighted bundle norm. After non-dimensionalisation one may again set $\tau = 1$.

Remark 2.5 (Dynamical origin of the cancellation condition). Equation (2.9) is not an independent hypothesis; it is the dynamical compatibility condition obtained from the identity $\frac{D}{Dt} v_1 =$

$-\Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi} = -v_2$ on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, derived in Appendix C. Thus, once the instantaneous conditions $v_1 = 0$ and $v_2 = 0$ are imposed, the first genuinely new first-order persistence condition is the vanishing of $\frac{D}{Dt}v_2$ along the induced flow. Because $\hat{\xi}$ is the vorticity direction, we have $\Omega \hat{\xi} = 0$; therefore the only term that can rotate the vorticity direction away from alignment is the anisotropic pressure torque $\Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi}$. The condition $v_2 = 0$ removes that torque, and the instability analysed later is encoded by the subsequent failure of v_2 itself to remain zero under the coupled dynamics.

Remark 2.6 (Physical interpretation of the defining constraints). The condition $v_1 = 0$ states that the unit vorticity direction is an eigenvector of the deformation tensor, so the strain does not instantaneously rotate $\hat{\xi}$ away from itself. The condition $v_2 = 0$ states that the deviatoric pressure Hessian exerts no transversal torque on that aligned direction. Thus $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ should be read not as a generic depletion regime, but as the *exact* locus where the strain-induced and pressure-induced transversal mechanisms relevant at first order are simultaneously eliminated.

The primary geometric object is therefore the exact alignment–cancellation manifold

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} := \{\tilde{U} \in \mathcal{F} : v_1(\tilde{U}) = 0, v_2(\tilde{U}) = 0\}. \quad (2.10)$$

To isolate exact degeneracy of the transversal spectrum in a smooth way, let $\tilde{S}_\perp(\tilde{U})$ denote the restriction of S to the 2-plane $\hat{\xi}^\perp$ in an orthonormal frame adapted to $\hat{\xi}$. We then define the scalar discriminant

$$v_3(\tilde{U}) := \text{disc}(\tilde{S}_\perp) := (\text{tr } \tilde{S}_\perp)^2 - 4 \det \tilde{S}_\perp. \quad (2.11)$$

The condition $v_3(\tilde{U}) = 0$ is equivalent to the coincidence of the two transversal eigenvalues. This defines the refined set

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{spec}} := \{\tilde{U} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} : v_3(\tilde{U}) = 0\}. \quad (2.12)$$

Remark 2.7 (Role of the refined spectral set). The set $\mathcal{M}_{\text{spec}}$ isolates an additional spectral degeneracy inside $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. It is not used in the proof of the escape or residence-time estimates, but it is recorded here because it cleanly separates the exact alignment–cancellation geometry from the further coincidence of transversal eigenvalues, which may be relevant in future higher-order normal-form analyses.

Lemma 2.8 (Smoothness and codimension). *Assume that λ is simple and that \tilde{U} lies in the open set where the aligned eigenvector $\hat{\xi}$ depends smoothly on S . Then the vertical differential of the intrinsic section $\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$ is surjective at every point of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. Consequently, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is a smooth submanifold of \mathcal{F} of codimension 4 and dimension 11. If, in addition, Dv_3 is independent of $D\Phi$ at a point, then $\mathcal{M}_{\text{spec}}$ is a smooth submanifold of codimension 5 and dimension 10 near that point.*

Proof. We give a local coordinate proof that respects the trace-free conditions. By the transitive action of $SO(3)$ on \mathbb{S}^2 , one may choose a local orthonormal frame adapted to the point under consideration so that $\hat{\xi} = e_1 = (1, 0, 0)^T$. This is only a local trivialisation of the intrinsic bundle picture from Remark 2.4; the surjectivity conclusion is frame-independent. Write the symmetric trace-free matrix S as

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda & a^T \\ a & \tilde{S} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $a \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and \tilde{S} is a symmetric 2×2 matrix. The trace condition $\text{tr } S = \lambda + \text{tr } \tilde{S} = 0$ implies $\text{tr } \tilde{S} = -\lambda$. No further restriction is imposed on \tilde{S} apart from symmetry; its three independent components together with λ and the two components of a give the five degrees of freedom of $\text{Sym}_0(3)$.

Similarly, write the deviatoric pressure Hessian H (also trace-free) as

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} \eta & h^T \\ h & \tilde{H} \end{pmatrix},$$

with $h \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and \tilde{H} symmetric 2×2 satisfying $\eta + \text{tr } \tilde{H} = 0$. The antisymmetric tensor Ω is written as

$$\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\omega_{\perp}^T \\ \omega_{\perp} & \Omega_{\perp} \end{pmatrix},$$

with $\omega_{\perp} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\Omega_{\perp} \in \mathfrak{so}(2)$ (one-dimensional).

The alignment condition $v_1 = \Pi^{\perp} S \hat{\xi} = 0$ gives directly $a = 0$ (two independent constraints). On the set $a = 0$, the vorticity direction condition $\Pi^{\perp} S \hat{\xi} = 0$ is satisfied, and $\lambda = \hat{\xi}^T S \hat{\xi}$ is indeed the eigenvalue.

Now compute v_2 when $a = 0$:

$$v_2 = \Pi^{\perp} H \hat{\xi} = (0, h)^T,$$

i.e., the two components of h . Thus $v_2 = 0$ gives $h = 0$ (two scalar constraints).

The Jacobian with respect to (a, h) is block-diagonal: $\partial v_1 / \partial a = I_2$ and $\partial v_2 / \partial h = I_2$. Therefore the combined 4×4 matrix is non-singular, and the rank is 4. In particular, the four defining equations are controlled directly by the transversal variables (a, h) ; no further independence check involving $\lambda, \tilde{S}, \omega_{\perp}, \Omega_{\perp}, \eta$, or \tilde{H} is needed. Hence $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ has codimension 4 and dimension $15 - 4 = 11$.

If we additionally impose $v_3 = \text{disc}(\tilde{S}_{\perp}) = 0$, this condition depends smoothly only on the aligned transversal 2×2 block of S . On the slice $a = 0$, the variables defining v_1 and v_2 are precisely the transversal components a and h , whereas v_3 probes the spectral degeneracy of \tilde{S}_{\perp} . Hence, at points where Dv_3 is not contained in the span of $D(v_1, v_2)$, the codimension increases by one, yielding codimension 5 and dimension 10 for $\mathcal{M}_{\text{spec}}$. \square

Dynamical meaning of the codimension

The fact that $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ has codimension 4 in \mathcal{F} has an immediate dynamical consequence: the exact alignment–cancellation conditions impose four independent instantaneous constraints on the extended state. Since the Euler evolution is deterministic, a generic trajectory will not satisfy these constraints unless special initial data or a fine-tuned dynamical balance is present.

Proposition 2.9 (Dynamical meaning of codimension). *Let $\tilde{U}(t)$ be a smooth lifted Euler trajectory and suppose that $\tilde{U}(t_0) \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. Then $\Phi(\tilde{U}(t_0)) = 0$ imposes four instantaneous algebraic constraints. For persistence on a nontrivial time interval, however, the first genuinely new first-order condition on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is*

$$\mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}(t_0)) := \left. \frac{D}{Dt} v_2(\tilde{U}(t)) \right|_{t=t_0} = 0.$$

Equivalently, once the defining relations $v_1 = 0$ and $v_2 = 0$ hold, the identity $\frac{D}{Dt} v_1 = -v_2$ shows that $\frac{D}{Dt} v_1$ vanishes automatically on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, so the first-order persistence problem reduces to the vanishing of the two independent components of $\frac{D}{Dt} v_2 \in \hat{\xi}^{\perp}$.

Proof. Membership in $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is equivalent to the four instantaneous equations $v_1 = 0$ and $v_2 = 0$, hence the codimension-4 statement remains purely geometric. For dynamics, Appendix C gives the identity

$$\frac{D}{Dt} v_1 = -\Pi^{\perp} H \hat{\xi} = -v_2 \quad \text{on } \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}.$$

Therefore, if $\tilde{U}(t_0) \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, then automatically $\frac{D}{Dt} v_1(\tilde{U}(t_0)) = 0$. The first-order persistence condition is thus not a new four-component restriction: the genuinely new requirement is that the remaining normal component $\frac{D}{Dt} v_2$ vanish at t_0 . Since $v_2 \in \hat{\xi}^{\perp}$, this contributes two independent scalar conditions in local orthonormal frames on $\hat{\xi}^{\perp}$. \square

2.3 Physical compatibility

The auxiliary variable H is not free along the actual PDE flow. To make the functional level precise, let

$$\mathfrak{X}_{\text{lift}}^s := H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3; \text{Sym}_0(\mathfrak{3})) \times H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3; \mathfrak{so}(\mathfrak{3})) \times C^1(\mathcal{O}_\omega; \mathbb{S}^2) \times H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3; \text{Sym}_0(\mathfrak{3})),$$

with $s > 5/2$, and define the physically compatible lifted graph

$$\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s := \left\{ (S, \Omega, \hat{\xi}, H) \in \mathfrak{X}_{\text{lift}}^s : H = \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2)) \right\}, \quad (2.13)$$

where

$$\mathcal{R} := \text{dev } \nabla^2(-\Delta)^{-1} \quad (2.14)$$

is the trace-free pressure operator generated by the Poisson equation. The operator \mathcal{R} has Fourier symbol $m(k) = \frac{k \otimes k}{|k|^2} - \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{I}$; being homogeneous of degree 0, it is bounded on H^s for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$ (see [12, Chapter IV] and [2, Chapter 2]).

For each particle label a and each smooth solution, let $X(a, t)$ be the corresponding Lagrangian trajectory and define the pointwise lifted evaluation map

$$\mathfrak{E}_a(t) := (S, \Omega, \hat{\xi}, H)(X(a, t), t) \in \mathcal{F}.$$

Thus the codimension-4 geometry of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is fibrewise in \mathcal{F} , whereas the physical dynamics enters through the family of evaluation curves $t \mapsto \mathfrak{E}_a(t)$ induced by smooth solutions.

Proposition 2.10 (Fibrewise geometry, physical compatibility, and invariance of the lifted graph). *Let $s > 5/2$ (geometric regularity). On bounded subsets of H^{s-1} , the map*

$$(S, \Omega) \mapsto \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2)) \quad (2.15)$$

is smooth as a map into H^{s-1} . In particular, $\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s$ is a smooth Banach submanifold of $\mathfrak{X}_{\text{lift}}^s$. Moreover, every classical Euler or Navier–Stokes solution induces, for each Lagrangian label a , a lifted evaluation curve $t \mapsto \mathfrak{E}_a(t) \in \mathcal{F}$ whose field-level representative stays in $\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s$ for all times of smooth existence. Consequently, the codimension and transversality analysis of $\Phi = (v_1, v_2)$ is carried out fibrewise in \mathcal{F} , while the dynamical statements of the paper are always interpreted along physically realised evaluation curves.

Proof. For $u \in H^s(\mathbb{R}^3)$ with $s > 5/2$, one has $S, \Omega \in H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3)$. Since $H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3)$ is an algebra at this threshold, $\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2) \in H^{s-1}$. The order-zero operator \mathcal{R} is bounded on H^{s-1} , so

$$H = \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2)) \in H^{s-1},$$

and the map $(S, \Omega) \mapsto H$ is smooth on bounded subsets of H^{s-1} . Therefore (2.13) defines a smooth graph and hence a smooth Banach submanifold.

If u is a classical Euler or Navier–Stokes solution, the pressure Poisson equation implies pointwise in time that its lifted fields satisfy $H = \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2))$. Therefore the associated lifted field trajectory remains in $\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s$ for every time on which the solution is smooth. Evaluating along $X(a, t)$ yields the pointwise lifted curve $\mathfrak{E}_a(t) \in \mathcal{F}$. This proves the stated invariance and clarifies the two levels used in the paper. \square

Remark 2.11 (Meaning of “local” in the lifted formulation). Throughout the paper, the term “local” refers to the defining equations in the finite-dimensional fibre variables $(S, \Omega, \hat{\xi}, H)$ once H has been lifted to an independent coordinate. The pressure law itself remains non-local and enters through the field-level graph constraint $\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s \subset \mathfrak{X}_{\text{lift}}^s$.

Proposition 2.12 (Structural stability). *Let $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be the exact alignment–cancellation manifold defined in (2.10). Consider a small perturbation of the defining equations of the form $\Phi_\delta = \Phi + \delta\Psi$, where Ψ is a smooth map with $\|\Psi\|_{C^1}$ sufficiently small. Then the perturbed zero set $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}^\delta = \{\tilde{U} : \Phi_\delta(\tilde{U}) = 0\}$ is, in a neighbourhood of a compact subset $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, a smooth manifold diffeomorphic to $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ and of the same codimension 4. In particular, the fibrewise geometric structure of the cancellation locus is robust under small perturbations of the defining constraints.*

Proof. On K , the differential $D\Phi$ has full rank 4 (Lemma 2.8). By the implicit function theorem, the zero set of a submersion is locally a smooth manifold. For a sufficiently small C^1 perturbation, the differential $D\Phi_\delta$ remains of full rank on a neighbourhood of K , and the zero set is a smooth manifold of the same dimension. The diffeomorphism follows from the standard stability of regular level sets. \square

Remark 2.13. Propositions 2.10 and 2.12 together show that the lifted fibre geometry is faithful to the physical dynamics when read through Lagrangian evaluation curves, and that the cancellation manifold is a structurally stable geometric object. This stability motivates the generic transversality hypothesis used later (Hypothesis 6.2).

3 Euler transversality and linear escape

We now analyse the induced Euler dynamics on the extended state. Along a smooth Euler solution, each fixed Lagrangian label a induces a lifted evaluation curve $t \mapsto \tilde{U}(t) = \mathfrak{E}_a(t) \in \mathcal{F}$, while the underlying field-level trajectory remains in $\mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s$. The identity from Appendix C implies that on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ one has $\frac{D}{Dt}v_1 = -v_2$, and hence $\frac{D}{Dt}v_1 = 0$ automatically once $v_2 = 0$. This motivates the following definition of the genuine first normal defect.

Definition 3.1 (First transversal defect along physical lifted curves). Let u be a smooth Euler solution on $[0, T]$, let $X(a, t)$ be a Lagrangian trajectory, and let $\tilde{U}_a(t) := \mathfrak{E}_a(t) \in \mathcal{F}$ denote its lifted evaluation curve. If $\tilde{U}_a(t_0) \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, define the first transversal defect by

$$\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t_0) := \left. \frac{d}{dt}v_2(\tilde{U}_a(t)) \right|_{t=t_0}. \quad (3.1)$$

The quantity in (3.1) is the first genuinely new normal derivative after the instantaneous constraints $v_1 = 0$ and $v_2 = 0$ have been imposed.

Definition 3.2 (Compact physically regular set relative to a bounded solution class). Fix $T > 0$, $M > 0$, and $s > 9/2$ as in the standing assumptions. A compact set $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is called *physically regular for Euler relative to the class $\mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$* if there exist a tubular neighbourhood $\mathcal{U}_K \subset \mathcal{F}$ and a constant $c_0(K) > 0$ such that, for every classical Euler solution $u \in \mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$ and every lifted Lagrangian evaluation curve $\tilde{U}_a(t)$ remaining in \mathcal{U}_K , one has

$$\|\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t_0)\| \geq c_0(K) \quad \text{whenever } \tilde{U}_a(t_0) \in K. \quad (3.2)$$

Remark 3.3 (Interpretation of the defect). The quantity $\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t_0)$ is evaluated along a physical Euler trajectory in the lifted fibre. Equivalently, one may decompose the induced Euler vector field along $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ into tangent and normal components with respect to the weighted metric from Remark 2.2; the defect above is precisely the first nontrivial normal Taylor coefficient governing whether the constraint $v_2 = 0$ persists.

Proposition 3.4 (Explicit representation of the first transversal defect on the physical graph). *Let $u \in \mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$ be a classical Euler solution, let $X(a, t)$ be a Lagrangian trajectory, and assume that $\tilde{U}_a(t_0) \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. Set*

$$q := \text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2).$$

Then the first transversal defect admits the pointwise representation

$$\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t_0) = \Pi^\perp \left(\frac{D}{Dt} H \right) \hat{\xi} \Big|_{(X(a,t_0), t_0)}. \quad (3.3)$$

On the physical lifted graph, where $H = \mathcal{R}q$, this becomes

$$\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t_0) = \Pi^\perp \left(\left[\frac{D}{Dt}, \mathcal{R} \right] q + \mathcal{R} \left(\frac{D}{Dt} q \right) \right) \hat{\xi} \Big|_{(X(a,t_0), t_0)}. \quad (3.4)$$

In particular, the physical-regularity hypothesis of Definition 3.2 is a non-vanishing assumption on an explicit, physically computable lifted quantity.

Remark 3.5 (Operational verification of physical regularity). Definition 3.2 is intentionally formulated at the level of the physical lifted dynamics, but Proposition 3.4 turns it into a concrete verification problem. In practice, for a fixed bounded family of smooth Euler trajectories, one checks physical regularity of a candidate compact set $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ by verifying four items on a tubular neighbourhood of K :

- (V1) $|\omega| \geq \omega_*(K) > 0$, so that $\hat{\xi}$ is smooth and the lifted bundle coordinates are well defined;
- (V2) the aligned eigenvalue remains simple, so the fibrewise geometry of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is smooth near K ;
- (V3) the explicit defect field in (3.4) extends continuously to the relevant physical tube;
- (V4) the resulting norm admits a strictly positive lower bound on K , uniformly over the chosen bounded family of solutions.

The present paper proves the obstruction theorem under this verification package, but does not claim that every smooth Euler flow must realise such a compact set.

Proof. By definition, $v_2 = \Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi}$. Differentiate along the lifted Lagrangian evaluation curve:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} v_2 = \left(\frac{D}{Dt} \Pi^\perp \right) H \hat{\xi} + \Pi^\perp \left(\frac{D}{Dt} H \right) \hat{\xi} + \Pi^\perp H \frac{D}{Dt} \hat{\xi}.$$

At points of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, Appendix C gives $\frac{D}{Dt} \hat{\xi} = \Pi^\perp S \hat{\xi} = v_1 = 0$, hence also $\frac{D}{Dt} \Pi^\perp = 0$. Since $v_2 = \Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi} = 0$ on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, the first and third terms vanish there, yielding (3.3). On the physical graph one has $H = \mathcal{R}q$, so

$$\frac{D}{Dt} H = \frac{D}{Dt} (\mathcal{R}q) = \left[\frac{D}{Dt}, \mathcal{R} \right] q + \mathcal{R} \left(\frac{D}{Dt} q \right),$$

which substituted into (3.3) gives (3.4). \square

Remark 3.6 (Status of Σ_{exc} and \mathcal{M}_{reg}). For expository convenience we retain the symbols

$$\Sigma_{\text{exc}} := \{ \tilde{U} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} : \text{the induced defect } \mathcal{N}_1 \text{ vanishes along a physical lifted curve through } \tilde{U} \} \quad (3.5)$$

and

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{reg}} := \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} \setminus \Sigma_{\text{exc}}. \quad (3.6)$$

These symbols should be read as shorthand for the physically realised part of the picture. The proved theorems below are stated directly for compact physically regular sets $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, precisely to avoid treating Σ_{exc} as an autonomous finite-dimensional object without further closure information.

Proposition 3.7 (No invariant compact subset in a physically regular set). *Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be physically regular in the sense of Definition 3.2. Then there is no nontrivial time interval $I \subset [0, T]$ of positive length such that a lifted Lagrangian evaluation curve satisfies $\tilde{U}_a(t) \in K$ for all $t \in I$.*

Proof. Suppose, for contradiction, that there exists such an interval $I = (t_0, t_1)$. Then $v_2(\tilde{U}_a(t)) = 0$ on I , so differentiating along the curve gives $\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t) = 0$ on I . This contradicts the lower bound (3.2). Hence no such interval exists. \square

Remark 3.8 (Norm used in Definition 3.2). Unless explicitly stated otherwise, $\|\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t_0)\|$ denotes the weighted bundle norm induced from Remark 2.4 after local trivialisation of $E \oplus E$. After non-dimensionalisation one may set $\tau = 1$, in which case this coincides locally with the Euclidean norm on the transversal coordinates. The lower bound $c_0(K)$ in Definition 3.2 is always understood relative to that fixed weighted norm and relative to the previously fixed class parameters (T, M, s) .

The next lemma converts small values of the defining map into small geometric distance to $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$.

Lemma 3.9 (Residual–distance equivalence). *Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set. Then there exist a tubular neighbourhood \mathcal{U}_K of K in \mathcal{F} and constants $c_1(K), c_2(K) > 0$ such that*

$$c_1(K) \text{dist}(\tilde{U}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}) \leq \|\Phi(\tilde{U})\| \leq c_2(K) \text{dist}(\tilde{U}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}) \quad \text{for all } \tilde{U} \in \mathcal{U}_K. \quad (3.7)$$

Proof. Since $D\Phi$ has rank 4 on the compact set K , the singular values of $D\Phi|_{N\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}}$ (the restriction to the normal bundle) are bounded above and away from zero: there exist $0 < \sigma_{\min} \leq \sigma_{\max} < \infty$ such that $\sigma_{\min}\|v\| \leq \|D\Phi(\tilde{U})v\| \leq \sigma_{\max}\|v\|$ for all normal vectors $v \in N_{\tilde{U}}\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ and all $\tilde{U} \in K$. By the implicit function theorem, there exists a tubular neighbourhood \mathcal{U}_K where the normal exponential map is a diffeomorphism. For $\tilde{U} \in \mathcal{U}_K$, let $\tilde{U}_* = \pi(\tilde{U}) \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be the orthogonal projection and $v = \tilde{U} - \tilde{U}_* \in N_{\tilde{U}_*}\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. Then $\Phi(\tilde{U}_*) = 0$ and by Taylor expansion $\Phi(\tilde{U}) = D\Phi(\tilde{U}_*)v + O(\|v\|^2)$. For $\|v\|$ sufficiently small (i.e., $\text{dist}(\tilde{U}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}) < \delta$), the linear term dominates, yielding

$$\frac{\sigma_{\min}}{2} \text{dist}(\tilde{U}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}) \leq \|\Phi(\tilde{U})\| \leq 2\sigma_{\max} \text{dist}(\tilde{U}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}).$$

Setting $c_1 = \sigma_{\min}/2$ and $c_2 = 2\sigma_{\max}$ completes the proof. \square

3.1 The non-local pressure contribution

Proposition 3.10 (Localized commutator and acceleration estimate). *Let $u \in \mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$ be a classical Euler or Navier–Stokes solution. Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set, and assume that there exists a tubular neighbourhood \mathcal{U}_K of K inside the lifted image of the flow on which $|\omega| \geq \omega_*(K) > 0$. For every $f \in H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3)$,*

$$\left\| \left[\frac{D}{Dt}, \mathcal{R} \right] f \right\|_{H^{s-2}} \leq C_s \|u\|_{H^s} \|f\|_{H^{s-1}}.$$

Consequently, there exists a bound $K_R(K, T) > 0$, depending only on $K, T, \omega_(K)$, and the fixed class bound M , such that for every Lagrangian particle trajectory remaining in \mathcal{U}_K ,*

$$\sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\| \frac{D^2}{Dt^2} v_2(\tilde{U}(t)) \right\| \leq K_R(K, T).$$

Proof. The operator $\mathcal{R} = \text{dev } \nabla^2(-\Delta)^{-1}$ is a matrix of order-zero singular integrals. Write $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}$ for brevity. The material derivative is $\frac{D}{Dt} = \partial_t + u \cdot \nabla$. Because \mathcal{R} is time-independent, $\partial_t \mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R} \partial_t$, so

$$\left[\frac{D}{Dt}, \mathcal{R} \right] f = [u \cdot \nabla, \mathcal{R}] f.$$

A refined Kato–Ponce commutator estimate (see [9] and [2, Theorem 2.86]) gives

$$\| [u \cdot \nabla, \mathcal{R}] f \|_{H^{s-2}} \leq C_s (\| \nabla u \|_{L^\infty} \| f \|_{H^{s-1}} + \| u \|_{H^s} \| f \|_{L^\infty}) \leq C_s \| u \|_{H^s} \| f \|_{H^{s-1}}.$$

To bound the second material derivative, write once more

$$v_2 = \Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi}, \quad \frac{D}{Dt} v_2 = \left(\frac{D}{Dt} \Pi^\perp \right) H \hat{\xi} + \Pi^\perp \left(\frac{D}{Dt} H \right) \hat{\xi} + \Pi^\perp H \frac{D}{Dt} \hat{\xi}.$$

Differentiating again shows that $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 v_2$ is a finite sum of terms of four types: products involving $\frac{D}{Dt} \Pi^\perp$ or $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 \Pi^\perp$, products involving $\frac{D}{Dt} \hat{\xi}$ or $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 \hat{\xi}$, terms containing $\frac{D}{Dt} H$ or $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 H$, and lower-order products of the preceding quantities. Since $\hat{\xi} = \omega/|\omega|$, each derivative of $\hat{\xi}$ is a smooth rational expression in ω , $\frac{D}{Dt} \omega$, and $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 \omega$, with denominators controlled by powers of $|\omega|$; the lower bound $|\omega| \geq \omega_*(K) > 0$ on \mathcal{U}_K therefore removes the only possible singularity.

For $u \in \mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$ with $s > 9/2$, one has $S, \Omega, q \in H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3)$, while their material derivatives lie in $H^{s-2}(\mathbb{R}^3)$. Because $H^{s-1}(\mathbb{R}^3)$ is an algebra, $H^{s-2}(\mathbb{R}^3) \hookrightarrow L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3)$, and \mathcal{R} is bounded on Sobolev spaces, all lower-order products produced by the previous expansion are pointwise bounded. Moreover,

$$\frac{D}{Dt} H = \left[\frac{D}{Dt}, \mathcal{R} \right] q + \mathcal{R} \left(\frac{D}{Dt} q \right)$$

is controlled in H^{s-2} by the commutator estimate above, and the same bookkeeping applied to $\frac{D}{Dt} q$ and $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 q$ yields a uniform bound for every contribution entering $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 H$. Consequently each term in the full expansion of $\frac{D}{Dt}^2 (\Pi^\perp H \hat{\xi})$ is uniformly bounded along trajectories staying inside \mathcal{U}_K , with a constant depending only on $K, T, \omega_*(K)$, and the fixed class bound M . \square

Remark 3.11 (Optimality of the regularity threshold). The threshold $s > 9/2$ chosen above is sufficient for all estimates but is not optimal. A more refined analysis using paradifferential calculus and sharper commutator estimates would allow the lower threshold $s > 7/2$ (see [2, Chapter 2] and [3]). Since our main results are qualitative (exclusion of Zeno accumulations), we do not pursue the optimal regularity; the condition $s > 9/2$ is a convenient simplifying assumption for the fixed bounded class $\mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$.

Remark 3.12 (Microlocal interpretation). The symbol computation in Appendix A shows that the principal symbol of $[u \cdot \nabla, \mathcal{R}]$ is $-\frac{1}{i} (\nabla u(x)^T k) \cdot \nabla_k m(k)$ with $m(k) = \frac{k \otimes k}{|k|^2} - \frac{1}{3} I$. Because $m(k)$ is a spherical harmonic of degree 2, its spherical gradient involves harmonics of degrees 1 and 3, which are orthogonal to the isotropic component. Hence the commutator does not create isotropic pressure contributions; this is the microlocal reason why the transversal defect interacts naturally with the anisotropic part of the pressure Hessian.

Figure 2: The trajectory $\tilde{U}(t)$ crosses the cancellation manifold $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ transversally at $t = t_0$ and leaves the ε -tubular neighbourhood after a time $\sim \varepsilon$. The linear escape estimate $\text{dist}(\tilde{U}(t), \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}) \gtrsim |t - t_0|$ prevents sustained trapping.

3.2 Linear escape

We now combine the positive first-order defect on K with the bounded second derivative of the defining map.

Proposition 3.13 (Linear escape from compact regular sets). *Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set, and let $t_0 \in [0, T]$ be such that $\tilde{U}(t_0) \in K$. Assume that the trajectory stays inside a tubular neighbourhood \mathcal{U}_K on which Proposition 3.10 applies. Then there exists $\tau = \tau(K, T) > 0$ such that for every t with $|t - t_0| \leq \tau$,*

$$\text{dist}(\tilde{U}(t), \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}) \geq \frac{c_0(K)}{2c_2(K)} |t - t_0|. \quad (3.8)$$

In particular, crossings of K are transversal and the distance to $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ grows at least linearly for short times after contact.

Proof. Since $\tilde{U}(t_0) \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, one has $v_2(\tilde{U}(t_0)) = 0$. Taylor expansion of v_2 at t_0 and Proposition 3.10 give

$$\|v_2(\tilde{U}(t))\| \geq |t - t_0| \|\mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}(t_0))\| - \frac{1}{2} K_R(K, T) |t - t_0|^2. \quad (3.9)$$

By Definition 3.2, $\|\mathcal{N}_1[\tilde{U}_a](t_0)\| \geq c_0(K)$. By continuity of the lifted trajectory and since $\tilde{U}(t_0) \in K \subset \mathcal{U}_K$, there exists $\tau_{\text{stay}} > 0$ such that $\tilde{U}(t) \in \mathcal{U}_K$ whenever $|t - t_0| \leq \tau_{\text{stay}}$. Choose

$$\tau := \min \left\{ \tau_{\text{stay}}, \frac{c_0(K)}{K_R(K, T)} \right\}. \quad (3.10)$$

Then (3.9) yields

$$\|v_2(\tilde{U}(t))\| \geq \frac{1}{2} c_0(K) |t - t_0|. \quad (3.11)$$

Since $\|\Phi(\tilde{U})\| \geq \|v_2(\tilde{U})\|$, applying the upper side of (3.7), namely $\|\Phi(\tilde{U})\| \leq c_2(K) \text{dist}(\tilde{U}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}})$, gives (3.8). \square

4 Exclusion of Zeno-type accumulation

We now derive the quantitative residence-time estimate. Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set and define

$$\Gamma_{T, \varepsilon}(K) := \{t \in [0, T] : \text{dist}(\tilde{U}(t), K) < \varepsilon\}. \quad (4.1)$$

Lemma 4.1 (Finite component bound). *Let $g \in C^2([0, T])$ be such that whenever $|g(t)| < \delta$ (for some $\delta > 0$), we have $|\dot{g}(t)| \geq a > 0$, and $|\ddot{g}(t)| \leq b$ on the whole $[0, T]$. Then the number of connected components of $\{t \in [0, T] : |g(t)| < \delta\}$ is bounded by*

$$N \leq \frac{2bT}{a} + 1.$$

Moreover, the length of each component is at most $2\delta/a$.

Proof. Let $I = (t_1, t_2)$ be a connected component of $G_\delta = \{t : |g(t)| < \delta\}$. By continuity, $|g(t_1)| = |g(t_2)| = \delta$ unless the component touches the boundary of $[0, T]$. On I , $|\dot{g}| \geq a > 0$ implies g is strictly monotone, so it can pass through at most one zero. The total variation of g on I is at least 2δ (from $-\delta$ to $+\delta$ or vice versa). Since $\int_I |\dot{g}| dt \geq a|I|$, we obtain $|I| \leq 2\delta/a$.

For the bound on the number of components, note that between any two components there must exist a point where $|g| \geq \delta$. Moreover, the derivative \dot{g} can change sign only after a time at least a/b (by the mean value theorem: if $\dot{g}(t_1) = v_1$ and $\dot{g}(t_2) = v_2$ with $v_1 v_2 < 0$, then there

exists τ with $\dot{g}(\tau) = 0$ and $|\tau - t_1| \geq |v_1|/b \geq a/b$. Hence the number of sign changes of \dot{g} is at most $\lfloor bT/a \rfloor + 1$. Each component of $\{|g| < \delta\}$ corresponds to an interval between two consecutive times where $|g| = \delta$ and where the sign of \dot{g} is fixed. Therefore the total number of components is at most $\lfloor bT/a \rfloor + 2$. In particular,

$$N \leq \frac{2bT}{a} + 1,$$

which is the convenient coarse bound used in the sequel. \square

Remark 4.2 (Sharpness versus sufficiency of Lemma 4.1). Lemma 4.1 is used only as a coarse counting device. The bound on the number of connected components is sufficient for the $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ residence-time law and is not claimed to be sharp in its constants. What matters for the main theorem is the combination of a uniform lower bound on the first derivative inside the tube and a uniform upper bound on the second derivative, not the optimisation of the counting constant.

Remark 4.3 (Return map interpretation). Let $\pi : \mathcal{U}_K \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be the orthogonal projection onto the cancellation manifold in a tubular neighbourhood. For a trajectory starting on K , the time needed to exit the ε -tube is at least $\tau_{\text{exit}} = \frac{2\varepsilon c_2(K)}{c_0(K)}$ by Proposition 3.13. After exiting, the trajectory may re-enter the tube only after traveling a positive distance in the normal direction. The number of such returns is bounded uniformly (Lemma 4.1), leading to the total residence time $O(\varepsilon)$.

Lemma 4.4 (Fixed-direction cover). *Let $F : K \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^3$ be continuous on a compact set K . Then there exist a finite open cover $K \subset \bigcup_{j=1}^J U_j$ and unit vectors $e_j \in \mathbb{S}^3$ such that*

$$e_j \cdot F(\tilde{U}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for all } \tilde{U} \in U_j.$$

Proof. For each $\tilde{U}_0 \in K$, choose $e_{\tilde{U}_0} := F(\tilde{U}_0) \in \mathbb{S}^3$. By continuity of F , there exists an open neighbourhood $U_{\tilde{U}_0}$ of \tilde{U}_0 such that $e_{\tilde{U}_0} \cdot F(\tilde{U}) \geq 1/2$ for all $\tilde{U} \in U_{\tilde{U}_0}$. Compactness of K yields a finite subcover $\{U_j\}_{j=1}^J$, and setting $e_j := e_{\tilde{U}_j}$ for a chosen base point $\tilde{U}_j \in U_j$ gives the claim. \square

Before stating the main residence-time theorem, let us isolate the mechanism proved so far. The compact lower bound on the first transversal defect supplies a uniform one-sided slope in a fixed normal direction, while Proposition 3.10 supplies a uniform second-derivative bound. Lemma 4.1 then implies that each visit to an ε -tube lasts at most order ε , and the number of such visits on $[0, T]$ is uniformly finite. The theorem below is precisely the quantitative synthesis of these ingredients.

Theorem 4.5 (Non-trapping residence-time estimate for Euler). *Let $u \in \mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$ be a classical solution of the three-dimensional incompressible Euler equations on the interval $[0, T]$. Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set. Then there exist $\varepsilon_0(K) > 0$ and $C(K, T) > 0$ such that for all $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_0(K)$,*

$$|\Gamma_{T, \varepsilon}(K)| \leq C(K, T)\varepsilon.$$

In particular, a regular Euler trajectory cannot spend a positive amount of total time in arbitrarily small tubular neighbourhoods of K .

Remark 4.6 (Dependence of constants and temporal validity). The proof yields the explicit choice

$$C(K, T) = C_{\text{geom}}(K) C_{\text{dyn}}(K, T),$$

with

$$C_{\text{geom}}(K) := J \frac{8c_2(K)}{c_0(K)}, \quad C_{\text{dyn}}(K, T) := \frac{8K_R(K, T)T}{c_0(K)} + 1.$$

Equivalently,

$$C(K, T) = J \left(\frac{8K_R(K, T)T}{c_0(K)} + 1 \right) \frac{8c_2(K)}{c_0(K)}.$$

Here J is the number of tubular charts in the chosen finite cover of K , $c_0(K)$ is the lower bound for the genuine first normal defect from Definition 3.2, $c_2(K)$ is the residual-distance equivalence constant from Lemma 3.9, and $K_R(K, T)$ is the localized second-material-derivative bound from Proposition 3.10. Relative to the fixed bounded class $\mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$, all of these constants depend only on K , T , M , and s (together with the chosen tubular neighbourhood), even though this dependence is suppressed in the notation. This factorisation makes explicit the division between the fibrewise geometry of the compact set and the global-in-time dynamical control entering the proof. The estimate holds for any $T > 0$ as long as the solution remains regular on $[0, T]$. Near a potential blow-up time T^* , the bound may deteriorate if $K_R(K, T)$ diverges, but it remains valid on every compact subinterval $[0, T] \subset [0, T^*)$.

Proof. We give a rigorous proof using a finite cover by tubular charts and local trivializations of the rank-2 bundle $E \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^2$. Since $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ is compact, choose a finite open cover $K \subset \bigcup_{j=1}^J U_j$ such that on each U_j there is a smooth orthonormal frame of $\hat{\xi}^\perp$, hence an identification $\vartheta_j : E|_{U_j} \rightarrow U_j \times \mathbb{R}^2$. On each $U_j \cap K$, the physical-regularity hypothesis and Proposition 3.4 give a continuous unit direction field

$$F_j(\tilde{U}) := \frac{\vartheta_j(\mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}))}{|\vartheta_j(\mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}))|} \in \mathbb{S}^1.$$

By compactness and Lemma 4.4, after shrinking the charts if necessary we may choose fixed unit vectors $e_j \in \mathbb{S}^1$ such that

$$e_j \cdot F_j(\tilde{U}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for all } \tilde{U} \in U_j \cap K.$$

Since $|\vartheta_j(\mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}))| \geq c_0(K)$ on $U_j \cap K$, this implies

$$|e_j \cdot \vartheta_j(\mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}))| \geq c_0(K)/2 \quad \text{for all } \tilde{U} \in U_j \cap K.$$

By continuity of the lifted vector field and of the chosen trivializations, we may shrink the tubular neighbourhood once more so that for every lifted Lagrangian evaluation curve intersecting U_j ,

$$|e_j \cdot \vartheta_j(\frac{d}{dt}v_2(\tilde{U}(t)))| \geq c_0(K)/4$$

whenever $\tilde{U}(t) \in U_j$. This is the precise origin of the factor $c_0(K)/4$ used below.

For each chart define the scalar observable

$$g_j(t) := e_j \cdot \vartheta_j(v_2(\tilde{U}(t))).$$

Then, while the trajectory remains in U_j ,

$$|\dot{g}_j(t)| = |e_j \cdot \vartheta_j(\frac{d}{dt}v_2(\tilde{U}(t)))| \geq c_0(K)/4,$$

and Proposition 3.10 gives $|\dot{g}_j(t)| \leq K_R(K, T)$ uniformly.

Now consider the residence set $\Gamma_{T, \varepsilon}(K)$. Choose ε_0 so small that the ε_0 -neighbourhood of K is contained in the union $\bigcup_j U_j$ and also inside the region where Lemma 3.9 holds. Then for any $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_0$, each connected component of $\Gamma_{T, \varepsilon}(K)$ lies entirely in one chart U_j . On that component, Lemma 3.9 gives $|g_j(t)| \leq \|v_2(\tilde{U}(t))\| \leq \|\Phi(\tilde{U}(t))\| \leq c_2(K)\varepsilon$.

Applying Lemma 4.1 to g_j with $\delta = c_2(K)\varepsilon$, we find that the length of each component is at most $2c_2(K)\varepsilon/(c_0(K)/4) = 8c_2(K)\varepsilon/c_0(K)$. Moreover, the number of components that can appear in a single chart U_j over the whole time interval $[0, T]$ is at most $\frac{2K_R(K,T)T}{c_0(K)/4} + 1 = \frac{8K_R(K,T)T}{c_0(K)} + 1$.

Since there are only finitely many charts J , the total number of components of $\Gamma_{T,\varepsilon}(K)$ is bounded by $J \left(\frac{8K_R(K,T)T}{c_0(K)} + 1 \right)$. Multiplying by the maximum component length gives

$$|\Gamma_{T,\varepsilon}(K)| \leq J \left(\frac{8K_R(K,T)T}{c_0(K)} + 1 \right) \frac{8c_2(K)\varepsilon}{c_0(K)} = C(K,T)\varepsilon,$$

with $C(K,T) = J \left(\frac{8K_R(K,T)T}{c_0(K)} + 1 \right) \frac{8c_2(K)}{c_0(K)}$. This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 4.7 (No persistent geometric skeleton in the Euler compact regular regime). *Under the hypotheses of Theorem 4.5, no compact physically regular set $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ can act as a persistent geometric skeleton for finite-time singularity formation in the sense that a trajectory would spend a positive amount of total time inside arbitrarily thin tubular neighbourhoods of K .*

Proof. Immediate from Theorem 4.5. \square

5 Navier–Stokes extension under small viscosity

We now consider the incompressible Navier–Stokes system

$$\partial_t u + (u \cdot \nabla)u = -\nabla p + \nu \Delta u, \quad \nabla \cdot u = 0, \quad \nu \geq 0. \quad (5.1)$$

The pressure law remains (1.2), so the fibrewise geometric definitions of \mathcal{F} , Φ , and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ are unchanged. The physically regular compact-set hypothesis is the Navier–Stokes analogue of Definition 3.2. The evolution of S and Ω acquires viscous terms:

$$\frac{DS}{Dt} = -S^2 - \Omega^2 + \Omega S - S\Omega - H + \nu \Delta S, \quad \frac{D\Omega}{Dt} = \Omega S - S\Omega + \nu \Delta \Omega.$$

The vorticity direction $\hat{\xi}$ now satisfies a material derivative with an explicit viscous correction stemming from $\Delta\omega$; this term is treated quantitatively below. The pressure Hessian H is still given by $H = \mathcal{R}(\text{tr}(S^2 + \Omega^2))$, independent of ν (since the pressure is determined by the same Poisson equation).

To control the dependence of the defect on viscosity, we impose intrinsic simplicity of the aligned eigenvalue together with non-degeneracy of the vorticity magnitude on a tubular neighbourhood of the compact set under consideration.

Assumption 5.1 (Intrinsic aligned-eigenvalue simplicity and vorticity non-degeneracy). *Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set. There exist a tubular neighbourhood $\mathcal{U}_K \subset \mathfrak{G}_{\text{phys}}^s$ of K , a constant $\gamma_K > 0$, and a constant $\omega_*(K) > 0$ such that for every lifted state $\tilde{U} = (S, \Omega, \hat{\xi}, H) \in \mathcal{U}_K$ the aligned eigenvalue*

$$\lambda(\tilde{U}) := \hat{\xi}^T S \hat{\xi}$$

is simple in the intrinsic sense

$$\text{dist}(\lambda(\tilde{U}), \sigma(S) \setminus \{\lambda(\tilde{U})\}) \geq \gamma_K, \quad |\omega| \geq \omega_*(K).$$

The first condition guarantees smooth dependence of the aligned eigendirection on S in a neighbourhood of K , while the lower bound on $|\omega|$ ensures that the viscous correction to the vorticity direction is well defined and uniformly controlled.

Lemma 5.2 (Viscous stability of the defect). *Assume $u \in \mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$, and let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set satisfying Assumption 5.1. Then there exists a constant $C_{\text{visc}}(K) > 0$ such that for all times t for which $\tilde{U}(t)$ remains in \mathcal{U}_K ,*

$$\|D\Phi(\tilde{U}(t))[X_{NS}(\tilde{U}(t))] - D\Phi(\tilde{U}(t))[X_E(\tilde{U}(t))]\| \leq \nu C_{\text{visc}}(K),$$

where X_{NS} and X_E denote the lifted Navier–Stokes and Euler dynamical fields, respectively. Consequently, if

$$0 \leq \nu < \nu_0(K) := \frac{c_0(K)}{2C_{\text{visc}}(K)},$$

then along the trajectory while it stays in \mathcal{U}_K ,

$$\|D\Phi(\tilde{U}(t))[X_{NS}(\tilde{U}(t))]\| \geq \frac{1}{2}c_0(K).$$

Proof. Write $\frac{D}{Dt_\nu} = \partial_t + u \cdot \nabla$. The vorticity equation for Navier–Stokes reads

$$\frac{D}{Dt_\nu} \omega = S\omega + \nu \Delta \omega.$$

Since $\hat{\xi} = \omega/|\omega|$ on \mathcal{U}_K and $|\omega| \geq \omega_*(K) > 0$, differentiation gives the exact identity

$$\frac{D}{Dt_\nu} \hat{\xi} = \Pi^\perp S \hat{\xi} + \nu \frac{1}{|\omega|} \Pi^\perp (\Delta \omega).$$

Hence

$$\frac{D}{Dt_\nu} \hat{\xi} - \frac{D}{Dt_0} \hat{\xi} = \nu \frac{1}{|\omega|} \Pi^\perp (\Delta \omega), \quad \left\| \frac{D}{Dt_\nu} \hat{\xi} - \frac{D}{Dt_0} \hat{\xi} \right\| \leq \nu \omega_*(K)^{-1} \|\Delta \omega\|_{L^\infty}.$$

Likewise,

$$\frac{D_\nu S}{Dt} = \frac{D_0 S}{Dt} + \nu \Delta S, \quad \frac{D_\nu \Omega}{Dt} = \frac{D_0 \Omega}{Dt} + \nu \Delta \Omega.$$

Because Φ is smooth in $(S, \Omega, \hat{\xi}, H)$, the difference between its derivatives along X_{NS} and X_E is a linear combination of $\nu \Delta S$, $\nu \Delta \Omega$, and $\nu |\omega|^{-1} \Pi^\perp \Delta \omega$, with coefficients given by first derivatives of Φ . These coefficients are uniformly bounded on \mathcal{U}_K because \mathcal{U}_K is a fixed tubular neighbourhood of the compact set K .

For $s > 9/2$ we have $\Delta S, \Delta \Omega, \Delta \omega \in H^{s-3}(\mathbb{R}^3) \hookrightarrow L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3)$. Therefore

$$\|\Delta S\|_{L^\infty} + \|\Delta \Omega\|_{L^\infty} + \|\Delta \omega\|_{L^\infty} \leq C_s \sup_{[0, T]} \|u(t)\|_{H^s}.$$

Combining the previous identities yields the claimed $O(\nu)$ bound, and the lower bound then follows from Definition 3.2 and the triangle inequality. \square

Remark 5.3 (Perturbative nature of the viscous correction). The constant $C_{\text{visc}}(K)$ depends on the C^1 -size of the defining map on the chosen tubular neighbourhood, on the spectral gap γ_K , on the vorticity lower bound $\omega_*(K)$, and on the a priori H^s -bound of the solution on $[0, T]$. Accordingly,

$$\nu_0(K) = \frac{c_0(K)}{2C_{\text{visc}}(K)}$$

should be read as an explicit perturbative threshold: viscosity is admissible precisely when the diffusive correction to the first normal defect is smaller than half of the inviscid compact lower bound. Equivalently, the local viscous time scale associated with the tube around K must remain longer than the inertial escape time encoded by $c_0(K)^{-1}$. This is the quantitative sense in which the Navier–Stokes statement is a small-viscosity continuation of the Euler obstruction.

The acceleration estimate of Proposition 3.10 remains valid for Navier–Stokes because the additional terms are lower order and $[\Delta, \mathcal{R}] = 0$ exactly. Relative to Euler, the first derivatives now contain the viscous corrections $\nu\Delta S$, $\nu\Delta\Omega$, and $\nu|\omega|^{-1}\Pi^\perp\Delta\omega$. On \mathcal{U}_K each of these is bounded by $C\nu\sup_{[0,T]}\|u\|_{H^s}$, so the same Taylor-expansion argument applies with constants uniform for $0 \leq \nu < \nu_0(K)$. Therefore the proof of Theorem 4.5 applies verbatim after replacing the inviscid first normal derivative by its Navier–Stokes counterpart, yielding:

Theorem 5.4 (Residence-time estimate for Navier–Stokes). *Let $u \in \mathcal{A}_s(T, M)$ be a classical Navier–Stokes solution on $[0, T]$. Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set satisfying Assumption 5.1. Then there exist $\nu_0(K) > 0$, $\varepsilon_0(K) > 0$, and $C(K, T) > 0$ such that for every $0 \leq \nu < \nu_0(K)$ and every $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_0(K)$,*

$$|\{t \in [0, T] : \text{dist}(\tilde{U}(t), K) < \varepsilon\}| \leq C(K, T)\varepsilon.$$

Proof. By Lemma 5.2, the first normal derivative for Navier–Stokes remains uniformly bounded below by $c_0(K)/2$ on the tubular neighbourhood \mathcal{U}_K whenever $0 \leq \nu < \nu_0(K)$. The commutator estimate of Proposition 3.10 and the discussion preceding the theorem provide the same uniform control of the second material derivative as in the Euler case, with constants depending additionally on the bounds from Assumption 5.1. Repeating the proof of Theorem 4.5 with the corresponding Navier–Stokes normal derivative gives the claimed residence-time bound. \square

6 Rigorous consequences and open geometric program

We now separate what the previous sections prove from what remains genuinely open.

Status map. For clarity, the logical status of the statements in this section is as follows.

- (S1) **Proved in the present paper:** the codimension-4 structure of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ in the simple-spectrum regime, the compact lower bound on the first normal defect on compact physically regular sets $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, the linear escape estimate, and the $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ residence-time bounds of Theorems 4.5 and 5.4.
- (S2) **Assumed only in the conditional exceptional-set discussion:** Hypothesis 6.2, which is not used anywhere in the proofs of Sections 2–5.
- (S3) **Open/programmatic:** the geometry and dynamical accessibility of Σ_{exc} and of the higher strata $\Sigma_2, \Sigma_3, \dots$

Proved consequences

Theorems 4.5 and 5.4 exclude sustained residence near compact regular subsets of the exact alignment–cancellation locus. The next corollary records this consequence in the sharp form needed for the singularity discussion.

Corollary 6.1 (Excluded compact regular scenario). *Let $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ be a compact physically regular set. Then no finite-time singularity mechanism for the three-dimensional Euler equations can rely on a trajectory spending a positive amount of total time inside arbitrarily small tubular neighbourhoods of K . Equivalently, the compact regular part of the exact alignment–cancellation locus cannot support persistent trapping in the sense relevant to a Zeno-type blow-up scenario. The same conclusion holds for Navier–Stokes under the assumptions of Theorem 5.4.*

Proof. If such a mechanism existed, then for a sequence $\varepsilon_n \downarrow 0$ the residence time inside the ε_n -tube of K would be bounded below by some $\delta > 0$ independent of n . But Theorems 4.5 and 5.4 give that this residence time is at most $C(K, T)\varepsilon_n$, which tends to 0 as $n \rightarrow \infty$, a contradiction. \square

The previous corollary leaves three logical possibilities for a singularity scenario compatible with the present analysis:

- (P1) approach to the exceptional set $\Sigma_{\text{exc}} \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, where first-order transversality degenerates;
- (P2) escape to unbounded regions of the state space, corresponding to loss of a priori gradient control;
- (P3) breakdown of regularity before any sustained compact exact alignment–cancellation regime can develop.

Open geometric locus Σ_{exc}

The results of this paper show that compact physically regular parts of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ (that is, compact sets on which the induced first transversal defect admits a uniform positive lower bound along physical lifted curves) cannot trap trajectories for a positive amount of total time. The genuinely open geometric issue is the nature of $\Sigma_{\text{exc}} = \{\tilde{U} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} : \mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}) = 0\}$. No statement of attraction is intended here: Σ_{exc} is introduced only as the unresolved degeneracy locus at which the first genuine normal defect vanishes. Everything in the remainder of this section is therefore either conditional, conjectural, or programmatic, and should be read strictly as describing what remains open after the proved compact-regular obstruction has been established.

Figure 3: Conditional stratification of the unresolved exceptional locus. The proved results exclude sustained trapping near compact physically regular subsets of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. Under Hypothesis 6.2, one expects successive codimension-2 drops $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} \supset \Sigma_{\text{exc}} \supset \Sigma_2$, corresponding to the successive vanishing of the genuine first normal defect and of the next normal derivative. The figure is purely schematic, is not used in any proof, and is included only to visualise the conjectural hierarchy discussed in Section 6.

Conjectural higher-order stratification

The first-order obstruction isolates the exceptional set Σ_{exc} . To go further, introduce the next normal derivative

$$\mathcal{A}_1(\tilde{U}) := \left. \frac{D}{Dt} \mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}(t)) \right|_{t=0},$$

and define the higher-order exceptional sets

$$\Sigma_2 = \{\tilde{U} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} : \mathcal{N}_1(\tilde{U}) = 0, \mathcal{A}_1(\tilde{U}) = 0\},$$

and inductively

$$\Sigma_{k+1} = \{\tilde{U} \in \Sigma_k : \mathcal{N}_k(\tilde{U}) = 0\},$$

where \mathcal{N}_k denotes the next nontrivial normal material derivative after restriction to Σ_k .

This yields a natural stratification

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} \supset \Sigma_{\text{exc}} \supset \Sigma_2 \supset \Sigma_3 \supset \dots,$$

where each stratum consists of configurations for which progressively higher-order normal Taylor coefficients vanish along the Euler flow.

Hypothesis 6.2 (Generic regular-value structure for the exceptional set). *Assume that, after choosing a local orthonormal trivialization of $E \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^2$, the map $\mathcal{N}_1 : \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ has 0 as a regular value. Then Σ_{exc} is a smooth embedded submanifold of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ of codimension 2 (hence dimension 9). If, in addition, the next normal derivative $\mathcal{A}_1|_{\Sigma_{\text{exc}}}$ also has 0 as a regular value, then Σ_2 has codimension 2 inside Σ_{exc} (hence dimension 7), and so on. This hypothesis is presented here as a natural geometric scenario rather than as a proved generic theorem.*

Remark 6.3. Hypothesis 6.2 isolates the geometric mechanism that would make the exceptional set into a smooth stratified object. We do not prove this hypothesis here. Its plausibility is supported by the structural stability of regular level sets (Proposition 2.12) and by the algebraic character of the defining maps, but a rigorous verification would require an explicit closure formula for the differential of the induced defect and of the higher-order normal derivatives along the physical lifted graph. That analysis lies beyond the present paper.

This stratification should be read as a conjectural geometric picture rather than as part of the proved main theorem. It provides a hierarchy of increasingly fine-tuned alignment–cancellation configurations and suggests the following open problem:

Open problem: Determine whether any of the higher strata Σ_k (for $k \geq 1$) can be dynamically accessible from regular initial data. In particular, does there exist a smooth Euler trajectory that reaches Σ_{exc} (or Σ_2) in finite time, and if so, what is the behaviour of the solution near such points? Recent finite-time singularity constructions (e.g., [6]) and numerical evidence (e.g., [8]) suggest that singular behaviour may involve increasingly anisotropic or degenerate configurations; whether these are captured by approach to Σ_{exc} or to higher strata in the present framework remains open.

Addressing this question would require a detailed analysis of the normal forms of the Euler equations near the cancellation manifold, a task that lies beyond the scope of the present work.

Remark 6.4 (Precise scope of the obstruction). The results of this paper do not assert global exclusion of blow-up. They show only that a compact regular exact alignment–cancellation regime cannot act as a persistent geometric skeleton for singularity formation. The unresolved locus is the exceptional set Σ_{exc} , where the genuine first normal defect vanishes and higher-order dynamics would have to be analysed.

Discussion and outlook

The results proved in this paper establish a precise obstruction to one specific class of geometric blow-up scenarios. They do *not* show that singularity formation is impossible; rather, they show that the compact regular part of the exact alignment–cancellation locus cannot function as a persistent geometric skeleton for singularity formation. The main gain is therefore not a broad regularity criterion, but a sharper structural conclusion: once the exact cancellation geometry is isolated in the lifted state space, one can prove codimension, a concrete formula for the first

transversal defect, transversality, linear escape, and an $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ residence-time law within a single framework.

From the editorial viewpoint relevant to *Journal of Geometry and Physics*, the genuine content of the paper is therefore geometric and dynamical at once: the nonlocal pressure Hessian is not discarded, but reorganised through a lifted finite-dimensional geometry that still remembers the physical compatibility constraint. This is precisely why the codimension calculation, the explicit defect formula, and the residence-time law belong to the same theorem package rather than to three unrelated observations.

What remains genuinely unresolved is sharply delimited: approach to the exceptional set Σ_{exc} , noncompact escape associated with unbounded growth of gradients, or loss of the simple-spectrum regime before a compact regular cancellation pattern can persist. The first of these is the most intrinsically geometric and appears to be the natural target for any future normal-form analysis beyond the compact regular regime.

Appendices

This appendix section collects the technical microlocal, tubular-neighbourhood, and derivation arguments used in the main text.

A Microlocal structure of the commutator

Let

$$P := \nabla^2(-\Delta)^{-1}, \quad \mathcal{R} = \text{dev } P.$$

The principal symbol of P is $p(k) = \hat{k} \otimes \hat{k}$, with $\hat{k} = k/|k|$, whereas the principal symbol of \mathcal{R} is

$$m(k) = \hat{k} \otimes \hat{k} - \frac{1}{3}\mathbf{I}.$$

The material derivative $L := \partial_t + u \cdot \nabla$ has principal symbol $\ell(x, k) = i u(x) \cdot k$. Standard pseudodifferential calculus gives

$$\sigma([L, \mathcal{R}])(x, k) = \frac{1}{i} \{\ell, m\} = \frac{1}{i} (\nabla_k \ell \cdot \nabla_x m - \nabla_x \ell \cdot \nabla_k m). \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Since m is independent of x , the term $\nabla_k \ell \cdot \nabla_x m$ vanishes identically. Moreover, $\nabla_x \ell = (\nabla u(x))^T k$. Hence

$$\sigma([L, \mathcal{R}])(x, k) = -\frac{1}{i} ((\nabla u(x))^T k) \cdot \nabla_k m(k).$$

Because m is homogeneous of degree 0, $\nabla_k m$ is homogeneous of degree -1 , so the commutator remains an operator of order 0. Using

$$\nabla_k m(k) = \frac{1}{|k|} \nabla_{\hat{k}} m(\hat{k}),$$

one obtains

$$\sigma([L, \mathcal{R}])(x, k) = -\frac{1}{i} ((\nabla u(x))^T \hat{k}) \cdot \nabla_{\hat{k}} m(\hat{k}).$$

The anisotropic symbol $m(\hat{k}) = \hat{k} \otimes \hat{k} - \frac{1}{3}\mathbf{I}$ belongs to the degree-two spherical harmonics. Its spherical gradient lies in the degree-one and degree-three sectors and is therefore orthogonal to the isotropic component. Consequently the leading symbol of the commutator is purely anisotropic: it does not generate an isotropic degree-zero contribution. This is the microlocal reason why the trace-free pressure operator couples naturally to the transversal defect used in the main text.

B Tubular coordinates and residence-time counting

For each compact physically regular set $K \subset \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, the smooth-submanifold structure of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ yields a tubular neighbourhood of K inside \mathcal{F} . The proof of Theorem 4.5 uses local trivializations of the rank-2 bundle carrying v_2 , rather than differentiating normal coordinates through a point-dependent linear transformation. The lower bound on the first derivative of v_2 coming from Definition 3.2 and the localized bound on the second derivative (Proposition 3.10) imply:

(A1) each visit to the ε -tube has duration at most $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$;

(A2) the number of visits on $[0, T]$ is finite and uniformly bounded (Lemma 4.1).

Combining these two facts yields the residence-time estimate of Section 4.

C Derivation of the cancellation condition $v_2 = 0$

We provide the detailed calculation leading to the expression of v_2 . Starting from the Euler equations, one has

$$\frac{DS}{Dt} = -S^2 - \Omega^2 + [\Omega, S] - H, \quad \frac{D\Omega}{Dt} = [\Omega, S],$$

where $[\Omega, S] = \Omega S - S\Omega$. The vorticity vector satisfies $\frac{D\omega}{Dt} = S\omega$. With $\hat{\xi} = \omega/|\omega|$, one obtains

$$\frac{D\hat{\xi}}{Dt} = \frac{1}{|\omega|} \frac{D\omega}{Dt} - \frac{\omega}{|\omega|^2} \frac{D|\omega|}{Dt}.$$

Using $\frac{D\omega}{Dt} = S\omega$ and $\frac{D|\omega|}{Dt} = \hat{\xi} \cdot S\omega = \lambda|\omega|$ (since on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$ we will have $v_1 = 0$ and $\lambda = \hat{\xi}^T S \hat{\xi}$), we get

$$\frac{D\hat{\xi}}{Dt} = S\hat{\xi} - \lambda\hat{\xi} = \Pi^\perp S\hat{\xi}.$$

Thus the evolution of the vorticity direction is governed solely by the transverse part of $S\hat{\xi}$.

Now differentiate $v_1 = \Pi^\perp S\hat{\xi}$ along the trajectory:

$$\frac{D}{Dt} v_1 = \frac{D\Pi^\perp}{Dt} S\hat{\xi} + \Pi^\perp \frac{DS}{Dt} \hat{\xi} + \Pi^\perp S \frac{D\hat{\xi}}{Dt}.$$

On $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, the condition $v_1 = 0$ implies $S\hat{\xi} = \lambda\hat{\xi}$, and the identity $\frac{D}{Dt} \hat{\xi} = \Pi^\perp S\hat{\xi}$ therefore yields

$$\frac{D\hat{\xi}}{Dt} = 0 \quad \text{on } \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}.$$

Differentiating $\Pi^\perp = I - \hat{\xi} \otimes \hat{\xi}$ gives

$$\frac{D\Pi^\perp}{Dt} = -\frac{D\hat{\xi}}{Dt} \otimes \hat{\xi} - \hat{\xi} \otimes \frac{D\hat{\xi}}{Dt},$$

so $\frac{D\Pi^\perp}{Dt} = 0$ as well on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$. Hence the first and third terms vanish directly, and we obtain the cleaner identity

$$\frac{D}{Dt} v_1 = \Pi^\perp \frac{DS}{Dt} \hat{\xi} \quad \text{on } \mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}.$$

Now insert the expression for $\frac{DS}{Dt}$:

$$\frac{DS}{Dt} \hat{\xi} = (-S^2 - \Omega^2 + \Omega S - S\Omega - H)\hat{\xi}.$$

Using $S\hat{\xi} = \lambda\hat{\xi}$, we compute:

$$\begin{aligned} -S^2 \hat{\xi} &= -S(\lambda\hat{\xi}) = -\lambda S\hat{\xi} = -\lambda^2 \hat{\xi}, \\ -\Omega^2 \hat{\xi} &= -\Omega(\Omega\hat{\xi}) = 0 \quad (\text{since } \Omega\hat{\xi} = 0), \\ \Omega S \hat{\xi} &= \Omega(\lambda\hat{\xi}) = \lambda\Omega\hat{\xi} = 0, \\ -S\Omega \hat{\xi} &= -S \cdot 0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\frac{DS}{Dt} \hat{\xi} = -\lambda^2 \hat{\xi} - H\hat{\xi}.$$

Applying Π^\perp annihilates the $-\lambda^2\hat{\xi}$ term because $\Pi^\perp\hat{\xi} = 0$. Therefore

$$\frac{D}{Dt}v_1 = -\Pi^\perp H\hat{\xi}.$$

Thus the condition for v_1 to remain zero (i.e., $\frac{D}{Dt}v_1 = 0$) along the Euler flow is

$$\Pi^\perp H\hat{\xi} = 0.$$

Defining $v_2 = \Pi^\perp H\hat{\xi}$ yields the cancellation condition stated in (2.9). This completes the derivation.

Physical interpretation. On $\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}$, the vorticity direction $\hat{\xi}$ is an eigenvector of the deformation tensor, so strain does not instantaneously rotate the vorticity direction away from alignment. The additional condition $v_2 = \Pi^\perp H\hat{\xi} = 0$ states that the deviatoric pressure Hessian also exerts no transversal torque on that direction. The quantity $\mathcal{N}_1 = \frac{D}{Dt}v_2|_{\mathcal{M}_{\text{cancel}}} = \Pi^\perp(\frac{D}{Dt}H)\hat{\xi}$ is therefore the first genuinely new dynamical signal measuring whether this exact cancellation geometry can persist. The escape mechanism proved in the body of the paper is precisely the statement that, on compact regular subsets, this signal does not vanish uniformly.

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Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data were used for the research described in this article. The manuscript is purely theoretical.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used ChatGPT (OpenAI) for language polishing and grammar checking, and GitHub Copilot for minor LaTeX syntax assistance. The author reviewed all AI-generated suggestions, and all mathematical content, proofs, and interpretations are the sole responsibility of the author.

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